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Temperature Resistant, Corrosion Tolerant Carburising Bearing Steel for Aero-engine Applications

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Abstract:	<p>The development of Very High Bypass Ratio (VHBR) aero-engines can contribute to fulfilling the goals of the Sustainable and Green Engines (SAGE) programme. The potential environmental benefits of the new aero-engine concept require increased speed and loading capabilities as compared to today's solutions.</p> <p>This paper describes the development of an advanced temperature resistant, corrosion tolerant steel for hybrid bearing rings for aero-engine applications. The target was for an increase in the hybrid bearing load capacity by 15% plus an increase of 25% in the rotation speed capability.</p> <p>In order to achieve the load capacity target, the steel rings of the hybrid bearing needed to be improved in terms of hardness, specifically hot hardness. The composition of Pyrowear® 675 was taken as a basis for the development and the alloying philosophy centred around the use of cobalt because of its beneficial effects on hot hardness.</p> <p>A series of small scale test melts were made with the initial compositions being modelled using ThermoCalc. The heat treatment response of the initial melts was used to define further test melts to refine the composition to a final target composition for an industrial 16 ton VIM-VAR melt. This patented novel composition was produced by a commercial steelmaker in the first half of 2018.</p> <p>The paper will describe how the final alloy composition was developed by combining modelling with experimentation. The next steps towards implementation of the concept will be outlined.</p>

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3 12th International Symposium on Rolling Bearing Steels – Progress in Bearing Steel
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6 **Temperature Resistant, Corrosion Tolerant Carburising Bearing Steel for**
7 **Aero-engine Applications**

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20 fulfilling the goals of the Sustainable and Green Engines (SAGE) programme. The
21 potential environmental benefits of the new aero-engine concept require increased
22 speed and loading capabilities as compared to today's solutions.
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26 tolerant steel for hybrid bearing rings for aero-engine applications. The target was for an
27 increase in the hybrid bearing load capacity by 15% plus an increase of 25% in the
28 rotation speed capability.
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31 to be improved in terms of hardness, specifically hot hardness. The composition of
32 Pyrowear® 675 was taken as a basis for the development and the alloying philosophy
33 centred around the use of cobalt because of its beneficial effects on hot hardness.
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36 A series of small scale test melts were made with the initial compositions being
37 modelled using ThermoCalc. The heat treatment response of the initial melts was used
38 to define further test melts to refine the composition to a final target composition for an
39 industrial 16 ton VIM-VAR melt. This patented novel composition was produced by a
40 commercial steelmaker in the first half of 2018.
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43 The paper will describe how the final alloy composition was developed by combining
44 modelling with experimentation. The next steps towards implementation of the concept
45 will be outlined.
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48 **Background**

49 The development of Very High Bypass Ratio (VHBR) aero-engines can contribute to
50 fulfilling the objectives of the Sustainable and Green Engines (SAGE) programme. The
51 potential environmental benefits of the new aero-engine concept requires rolling
52 bearings with increased speed and loading capabilities as compared to today's
53 solutions. In order to address this development need, SKF Aerospace France initiated
54 the "ARCTIC" project, which is a European Union (EU) funded project with the objective
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to develop advanced steels for hybrid bearings i.e. bearings with steel rings and ceramic rolling elements.

The acronym ARCTIC comes from the project title “Advanced Bearing Technologies to Increase Capabilities” where “increase capabilities” refers to an increase in the hybrid bearing load capacity by 15 to 30% and an increase of 25% in the rotation speed capability. In order to achieve the load capacity targets, the steel rings of the hybrid bearings need to be improved in terms of hardness, specifically hot hardness. There were two approaches to this:

- VIM-VAR (Vacuum Induction Melting – Vacuum Arc Remelting) processing of novel alloys to achieve a 15% load capacity increase
- PM-HIP (Powder Metallurgy with Hot Isostatic Pressing) of novel alloys to achieve a 30% load capacity increase

This paper describes the development of the novel VIM-VAR steel, which was named “Arctic 15” because of the target increase in load capacity.

Alloy Design

The concept of an “Ideal SKF Aero-engine Bearing Steel” was developed in order to translate the VHBR aero-engine application conditions into the metallurgical requirements for the steel rings for the hybrid bearings. The main outcomes of this study were that the steel should:

- Be manufactured using “clean steel” technology e.g. VIM-VAR
- Be corrosion tolerant
- Be resistant to through fracture
- Be dimensionally stable in the application
- Have an increased static capacity
- Have a compressive residual stress in the case
- Have an extended rolling contact fatigue life

It was decided to use the Pyrowear® 675 (P675) steel as a basis for the alloy design and the nominal P675 composition according to AMS 5930B is shown in table 1.

Steel	C	Si	Mn	Cr	Mo	Ni	V	Co
P675	0.070	0.40	0.75	13.0	2.0	2.5	0.6	5.5

Table 1. Nominal composition of P675. Values in wt%

P675 was developed as a low carbon aerospace steel, originally designated as EX00098 and patented in 1991 by Carpenter Technology Corporation [Refs.1&2]. The original design goals for the steel technology were:

- Core microstructure $K_{IC} > 44 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$
- Surface hardness HRC 59 at 329°C (625°F)
- Corrosion resistance equal to 440C

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3 The P675 steel technology was compared to M50NiL and several corrosion resistant
4 steels in a detailed program published in 1998 [Ref.3] and P675 was also part of the
5 seminal comparison of aerospace bearing steels published in 2002 [Ref.4].
6

7
8 After carburizing or carbonitriding, P675 can be Low Temperature Tempered (LTT) at
9 316°C (600°F) for corrosion resistance or High Temperature Tempered (HTT) at 496°C
10 (925°F) for increased surface hardness [Ref.5].
11

12 For the development of the Arctic 15 steel, the focus was on the increase of static
13 capacity which can be translated into an increase of surface hardness at both room
14 temperature and at elevated temperature, assuming a sufficient hardening depth is
15 achieved. From an alloying perspective, it was decided to focus on cobalt as an element
16 which could achieve this aim [Ref.6]. From a heat treatment perspective, the focus was
17 clearly on the HTT option, with a preference for carbonitriding over carburising to further
18 increase the surface hardness [Ref.5].
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21 The alloy design was an iterative process which combined theoretical modelling with
22 experimentation using small scale melts. The main modelling tools were
23 Thermo-Calc, using the TCFE9 database, and the following two equations for the
24 “nickel equivalent” (Ni_{eq}) and “chromium equivalent” (Cr_{eq}) values:
25

$$26 \quad Ni_{eq} = Ni + Co + 0.5Mn + 30C \quad [Ref.7]$$

$$27 \quad Cr_{eq} = Cr + 2Si + 1.5Mo + 5V \quad [Ref.7]$$

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31 The Ni_{eq} value was used as an indication of the M_s temperature where the aim was not
32 to unduly suppress the M_s temperature. An excessively low M_s could lead to a high
33 retained austenite content in the thermochemically treated surface, which could reduce
34 the compressive residual stress in the case and potentially adversely affect the
35 dimensional stability of the product. The Cr_{eq} value was used, in conjunction with the
36 Ni_{eq} value, as an indication of the likelihood of δ -ferrite formation and the target was to
37 have a similar Cr_{eq} value to that of standard P675.
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40 One of the known issues with P675 is the long carburising times (>100 h) which are a
41 consequence of the modest process temperatures used in order to avoid excessive
42 grain growth and undesirable surface microstructures. This was an additional
43 consideration in the alloy design and led to the use of niobium micro-alloying additions
44 as these could result in niobium-rich precipitates which could pin the grain boundaries.
45 This is illustrated in figures 1 and 2, where figure 1 shows the phase diagram for the
46 standard P675 composition and figure 2 shows the phase diagram for a niobium micro-
47 alloyed composition (alloy B in table 2). The main difference is that, in figure 2, there is
48 a line below which it is predicted that niobium carbides will be formed, as indicated by
49 the arrow.
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54 *Figure 1. Phase diagram for P675*
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Figure 2. Phase diagram for alloy B with niobium micro-alloying

First Melt Series

The first series of three 60 kg VIM melts were made by Liberty Speciality Steels, UK. The compositions of these melts are shown in table 2, with the nominal composition of P675 shown for reference. In addition to the compositions, the Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} values are also shown.

Steel	C	Si	Mn	Cr	Mo	Ni	V	Nb	Co	Ni_{eq}	Cr_{eq}
P675	0.070	0.40	0.75	13.0	2.0	2.5	0.6	-	5.5	10.5	19.8
A	0.076	0.18	0.47	12.42	2.0	0.53	0.6	0.032	7.2	10.2	18.8
B	0.069	0.16	0.47	12.05	2.5	1.04	0.5	0.030	7.23	10.6	18.6
C	0.054	0.17	0.51	13.4	2.74	1.54	0.53	0.032	8.16	11.6	20.5

Table 2. Experimental melt compositions. Composition values in wt%

All three experimental alloys have a significantly higher cobalt content than P675 and all three are micro-alloyed with niobium. The other main composition differences between the experimental alloys and P675 are the molybdenum and nickel contents which were adjusted to maintain similar Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} values.

Liberty Speciality Steels investigated the homogenising response of the three experimental steels in the temperature range 1100 to 1250°C. Based on this information, the 60 kg ingots were rolled to an intermediate dimension and then homogenised at 1150°C for 30 hours. After cooling, the variants were re-heated to 1150°C and rolled to 35 mm diamond bar.

Although the Thermo-Calc modelling predicted microstructures which were free of δ -ferrite at equilibrium, it was clear from the metallographic investigation that δ -ferrite was actually present. This is an indication of the limitations of using thermodynamic assumptions in modelling steels and of using commercial databases for novel, highly alloyed steels.

The δ -ferrite content of the three steels was assessed at SKF by electrolytic etching in 20% sodium hydroxide to reveal the phase, as described in the aerospace standard AMS 2315G. Micrographs were made of the microstructures and the δ -ferrite content was determined by image analysis using ImageJ software, as illustrated in figure 3 and figure 4 for alloy A. It should be commented that the δ -ferrite assessment was based on an area within the micrograph to avoid any corner effects. The results for the three experimental melts can be seen in table 3.

Figure 3. δ -ferrite in Alloy A

Figure 4. Image analysis in ImageJ

Steel	δ -ferrite content (area %)
A	8.5
B	1.1
C	2.6

Table 3. Area fraction of δ -ferrite in the experimental melts

Taking 3% as a target maximum value based on information for P675, the δ -ferrite content of alloy A was clearly excessive while that of alloys B and C was in the acceptable range.

At this stage of the development, it was decided that the final thermochemical heat treatment for the Arctic steels would be carbonitriding rather than carburising. The addition of nitrogen, as well as carbon, to the surface gives a number of potential benefits in terms of hardness, hot hardness and corrosion resistance, as evidenced by previous investigations on carbonitrided P675 [Ref.5]. An indication of the effect of nitrogen on the corrosion resistance is given by the Pitting Resistance Equivalent Number (PREN), where:

$$\text{PREN} = \text{Cr} + 3.3\text{Mo} + 30\text{N} \quad [\text{Ref.8}]$$

Although the referenced PREN is based on austenitic stainless steels and is only valid for the elements in solid solution in the steel matrix, it indicates that carbonitriding offers the possibility to reduce the chromium content in the steel whilst maintaining the pitting corrosion resistance. Lowering the chromium content has the advantage of reducing the likelihood of δ -ferrite being present in the microstructure.

Second Melt Series

A second series of compositions was designed using Thermo-Calc in combination with the Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} equations. The test melts were again produced by Liberty Speciality Steels and the compositions and Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} values can be seen in table 4.

Steel	C	Si	Mn	Cr	Mo	Ni	V	Nb	Co	Ni_{eq}	Cr_{eq}
P675	0.070	0.40	0.75	13.0	2.0	2.5	0.6	-	5.5	10.5	19.8
D	0.054	0.16	0.47	11.19	3.46	1.02	0.51	0.033	7.18	10.1	19.3
E	0.050	0.15	0.47	12.37	2.49	1.83	0.51	0.033	6.51	10.1	19.0
F	0.050	0.21	0.68	11.45	1.82	0.56	1.01	0.034	8.06	10.5	19.7
G	0.040	0.16	0.47	11.31	3.48	0.54	0.51	0.033	8.47	10.4	19.4

Table 4. Experimental melt compositions. Composition values in wt%

Alloy D was an extension of alloy B in that the cobalt content was maintained but the molybdenum was increased by 1% and the chromium decreased by 1% to give a potentially higher PREN.

Alloy E has a more modest increase in cobalt content compared to alloy B to give an indication of the effect on hardness and hot hardness.

Alloy F was primarily alloyed for hardness and hot hardness, hence the high cobalt and vanadium contents. The chromium and nickel contents were reduced to maintain the Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} levels at the target values.

Alloy G had a high cobalt content for hardness and hot hardness and a high molybdenum content for corrosion resistance. Again, the chromium and nickel contents have been reduced to balance the Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} values.

For logistical reasons, the second series of ingots produced by Liberty Speciality Steels were processed at SWERIM, Sweden. The ingots were homogenised at 1150°C for 38 hours and hot forged to 75 mm squares. These were then reheated to 1000°C and rolled to 28 mm square bar.

As before, the δ -ferrite content was assessed at SKF by electrolytic etching in sodium hydroxide and image analysis using the ImageJ software. The δ -ferrite contents can be seen in table 5.

Steel	δ -ferrite content (area %)
D	12.9
E	<1
F	10.2
G	14.3

Table 5. Area fraction of δ -ferrite in the experimental melts

Only alloy E had an acceptably low level of δ -ferrite of these four experimental compositions. Although the somewhat low carbon contents of alloys D, F and G will have contributed to the high δ -ferrite contents, this is not the whole explanation as alloy E only contained 0.05% carbon.

In order to assess the effect of the higher cobalt content on the surface hardness level, specimens from all seven experimental alloys were low pressure carburised (LPC), rehardened, sub-zero treated and tempered using a standard recipe for P675. The heat treatments were performed under the supervision of SKF Aerospace USA. Given that the aim was for a high surface hardness, the tempering treatments were carried out at 496°C (925°F), which is the HTT variant for P675. The hardness profiles can be seen in figure 5, which also includes a typical hardness profile for P675 in the HTT condition. Figure 5 shows that all seven experimental alloys had significantly higher surface hardness values than would be expected from standard P675. It should be noted that

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3 the surface hardness values and surface microstructures were judged at a depth of
4 0.3 mm to represent the position of the finished bearing ring raceway.
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6 Although the case depth (CD) at HV 653 is marked in figure 5, no conclusions were
7 drawn about the relative case depths at this stage.
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11 *Figure 5. Hardness profiles for the experimental alloys*
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13 The carburised microstructures were metallographically examined on transverse cross-
14 sections after polishing and etching in the Modified Curran etch, which is an aqueous
15 solution of hydrochloric acid and iron (III) chloride (FeCl_3). A number of the alloys had
16 surface microstructures which were comparable to standard P675 in that there was a
17 relatively high volume fraction of relatively fine carbides, as can be seen in figure 6. It
18 was noted that some of the alloys had features which can be described as “rod-like”
19 carbides and an example of such a microstructure is shown in figure 7. These “rod-like”
20 carbides are unacceptable to some aerospace customers. None of the carburised
21 surfaces showed any indication of the presence of δ -ferrite but the core δ -ferrite content
22 was basically the same as that measured previously and listed in tables 3 and 5.
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27 *Figure 6. Surface microstructure of alloy G*
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31 *Figure 7. Rod-like carbides in alloy B*
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33 While figure 5 indicates that the cobalt additions of 6.51 to 8.47% gave an increase in
34 the carburized surface hardness, figure 8 shows that there was no real correlation
35 between the surface hardness and the cobalt content in this composition range.
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39 *Figure 8. Cobalt content and surface hardness*
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41 Of course, the presence of significant quantities of the relatively soft retained austenite
42 phase may have influenced the results in figure 8. Retained austenite was not clearly
43 visible in the surface microstructures using light optical microscopy but the carburised
44 specimens from alloys D and G were assessed using X-ray diffraction and were found
45 to have 8% retained austenite.
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48 The surface residual stress profiles of the carburised specimens from alloys D and G
49 were also determined. It was shown that there was a modest compressive residual
50 stress in the case, as can be seen in figure 9.
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54 *Figure 9. Residual stress profiles for alloy D and alloy G*
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A summary of the results of the carburised specimens from the seven experimental alloys is shown in table 6. The grain size was assessed according to ASTM E112.

Steel	Surface Hardness	Case Depth	Core Hardness	ASTM Grain Size	Core δ -ferrite	Comments
A	HV 820	1.6 mm	HV 450	8.0	8.5%	Rod-like carbides
B	HV 840	1.7 mm	HV 450	5.5	1.1%	Rod-like carbides
C	HV 850	1.4 mm	HV 430	7.5	2.6%	Rod-like carbides
D	HV 855	1.7 mm	HV 410	8.0	12.9%	-
E	HV 820	1.5 mm	HV 415	4.5	<1%	Large core grains
F	HV 820	1.5 mm	HV 400	6.5	10.2%	-
G	HV 850	1.7 mm	HV 400	8.0	14.3%	-

Table 6. Summary of the characteristics of the experimental alloys

The shaded cells in table 6 indicate that all seven experimental alloys have either an undesirable feature, such as a high core δ -ferrite content, or a less desirable feature, such as a lower surface hardness. In order to progress, it was decided to make further test melts based on the most promising results from table 6. Alloys A, B and C were rejected as candidates because of the tendency to form rod-like carbides in the carburised surface. Alloys E and F were rejected because of the relatively low surface hardness as this is contrary to the primary aim of the ARCTIC project to increase the surface hardness. This elimination process left alloys D and G as the candidate compositions as the basis for the new melts. The main issue with alloys D and G was the high δ -ferrite content in the core but this was regarded as a solvable problem.

Third Melt Series

With reference to the Schneider diagram in figure 10, it can be seen that to reduce the δ -ferrite content for a given Cr_{eq} value, the Ni_{eq} value should be increased, as indicated by the arrow [Ref.7]. Basically, the aim is move further away from the “Ferrite” field.

Figure 10. Schneider diagram [Ref.7]

One simple way to increase the Ni_{eq} is to increase the carbon content. Obviously, increasing the core carbon content may reduce the core toughness and also reduce the magnitude of the compressive residual stress in the case. However, it was thought that a modest increase in carbon content to a target value of 0.12% would achieve a balance between the δ -ferrite content in the microstructure and the mechanical properties. This became the target carbon content for a new melt composition based on alloy D and alloy G.

Another way to increase the Ni_{eq} value is to increase the nickel content, of course. A review of the results from the seven experimental melts indicated that there was a correlation between the nickel content and the δ -ferrite content, as shown in figure 11. The correlation is somewhat weak, particularly when considering the spread in δ -ferrite contents for the two alloys with around 1% nickel. Despite this, the concept of

nickel alloying was used to develop a new composition based on the predicted Thermo-Calc phase diagram and using the Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} equations.

A higher nickel content would potentially reduce the M_s temperature and, therefore, reduce the magnitude of the compressive residual stress in the case if the retained austenite content increased significantly. However, a higher nickel content would be expected to be beneficial for the toughness properties.

Figure 11. Correlation between nickel content and δ -ferrite content

The new compositions were produced as 8 kg VIM ingots by The Advanced Steel Processing Group at WMG, The University of Warwick, UK. The first higher carbon ingot, alloy H, cracked during the homogenising process. This cracking was thought to be due to a high heating rate so a new melt, alloy I, was made. Alloy J was the melt with the increased nickel content and both alloy I and alloy J were successfully homogenised without ingot cracking using a reduced heating rate. All three alloys were homogenised at 1150°C for 24 hours.

The compositions of the three melts can be seen in table 7, along with the Ni_{eq} and Cr_{eq} values.

Steel	C	Si	Mn	Cr	Mo	Ni	V	Nb	Co	Ni_{eq}	Cr_{eq}
P675	0.070	0.40	0.75	13.0	2.0	2.5	0.6	-	5.5	10.5	19.8
H	0.14	0.21	0.3	11.68	3.46	0.28	0.34	0.034	8.55	13.2	19.0
I	0.11	0.2	0.22	11.47	3.51	0.29	0.55	0.036	8.49	12.2	19.9
J	0.077	0.2	0.24	11.4	3.38	1.56	0.5	0.04	8.19	12.2	19.4

Table 7. Experimental melt compositions. Composition values in wt%

As before, the Cr_{eq} value was targeted to be similar to that of standard P675. The Ni_{eq} was significantly higher than that of P675 and the previous seven experimental melts in order to suppress the formation of δ -ferrite.

The homogenised ingots were forged at 1150°C to 30 mm square section bar at Liberty Speciality Steels. For alloy H, only half of the cracked ingot was forged.

The microstructures of the bars were assessed using both the Modified Curran etch and electrolytic etching with 20% sodium hydroxide. Alloy I was found to have a high δ -ferrite content, measured as 8% by area. Alloy H was found to have a second phase which tended to be present in the positive segregation bands. See figure 12. Despite SEM EDS investigations, it was not clear if this second phase was δ -ferrite or carbide but it was clear that this phase was undesirable. The microstructures of the bars from alloy J were free from δ -ferrite or any other second phases which meant that alloy J was automatically the preferred composition of the three alloys.

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3 *Figure 12. Second phase in alloy H*
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6 As before, specimens from alloy J were supplied to SKF Aerospace USA for LPC,
7 rehardening, sub-zero treating and tempering according to a standard recipe for P675.
8 In this case, the load was tempered at 315°C (600°F), which is the LTT treatment. A
9 proportion of the specimens were given an additional tempering at 496°C (925°F) to
10 give an indication of the hardness which could have been achieved with a HTT
11 treatment. The hardness profiles can be seen in figures 13 and 14 and it is clear that
12 alloy J has a higher surface hardness and deeper case depth than the standard P675
13 specimens which were in the same furnace load. It can be speculated that
14 carbonitriding of alloy J would result in a further increase in surface hardness and case
15 depth, suggesting that shorter processing times could be used to achieve a given case
16 depth.
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20 *Figure 13. Hardness profiles of alloy J and P675 (LTT)*
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25 *Figure 14. Hardness profiles of alloy J and P675 treated at 496°C*
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27 The composition of alloy J was used as a basis for a purchasing specification for an
28 industrial VIM-VAR melt of the Arctic 15 steel. This melt was produced by voestalpine
29 BÖHLER Edelstahl, Austria, in 2018 and the melt composition is shown in table 8. The
30 melt composition conforms to the SKF patent for this steel [Ref.9].
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Steel	C	Si	Mn	Cr	Mo	Ni	V	Nb	Co	Ni _{eq}	Cr _{eq}
Arctic 15	0.10	0.18	0.37	11.06	3.17	1.50	0.48	0.03	8.09	12.8	18.6

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37 *Table 8. Composition of the industrial VIM-VAR Arctic 15 melt.*
38 *Composition values in wt%*
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40 **Next steps**

41 The Arctic 15 VIM-VAR melt will be used to determine the basic mechanical and
42 physical property data for this novel steel and to develop the carbonitriding process. The
43 corrosion resistance capabilities of the carbonitrided surface will be investigated. The
44 RCF performance will be assessed on components, such as flat washers [Ref.10], and
45 on bearings, where the bearing test conditions will be representative of the aero-engine
46 application.
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49 **Conclusions**

50 A novel cobalt-alloyed steel composition has been developed which has been shown to
51 have a significantly higher surface hardness than Pyrowear® 675 in the carburised and
52 secondary hardened condition.
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3 The surface hardness of the novel steel, called Arctic 15, could be further increased by
4 carbonitriding and secondary hardening.
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7 This work has shown that an iterative combination of theoretical modelling and
8 experimentation can be an efficient methodology for developing new steel compositions.
9

10 Mechanical property tests, corrosion tests and rolling contact fatigue tests will be
11 performed to confirm that the Arctic 15 steel can achieve the increased speed and load
12 capacity targets required for hybrid bearings for future VHBR aero-engines.
13

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16 Commission as part of the EU “Clean Sky 2” programme.
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18
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24 Advanced Steel Processing Group at WMG, The University of Warwick,
25 SKF Aerospace USA and voestalpine BÖHLER Edelstahl are gratefully acknowledged
26 by the authors.
27

28 **References**

- 29
30 Ref.1 D.E. Wert & R.M. Hemphill, Carpenter Technology Corporation, US 5002729,
31 “Case hardenable corrosion resistant steel alloy and article made therefrom”
32 Ref.2 T.J. McCaffrey & D.E. Wert, “Development of a Stainless Corrosion Resistant
33 Carburizing Bearing Steel”, Creative Use of Bearing Steels, ASTM STP 1195,
34 J.J.C. Hoo, Ed., Americal Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1993,
35 pp. 137-148
36 Ref.3 D. Grant et al, “High Temperature Aircraft Turbine Engine Bearing and
37 Lubrication System Development”, Bearing Steels: Into the 21st Century, ASTM
38 STP 1327, J.J.C. Hoo & W.B. Green, Eds., Americal Society for Testing and
39 Materials, 1998
40 Ref.4 M.A. Ragen et al, “A Comparision of the Mechanical and Physical Properties of
41 Contemporary and New Alloys for Aerospace Bearing Applications”, Bearing
42 Steel Technology, ASTM STP 1419, J.M. Beswick, Ed., American Society for
43 Testing and Materials International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2002
44 Ref.5 H. Trivedi et al, “Heat Treatment Process for Martensitic Stainless Steel
45 Pyrowear 675 for Improved Corrosion Resistance”, Bearing Steel Technologies:
46 10th Volume, Advances in Steel Technologies for Rolling Bearings, ASTM STP
47 1580, John M. Beswick, Ed., pp465-484
48 Ref.6 J.L. Maloney & C.M. Tomasello, Latrobe Steel Company, US 5424028(A)
49 Ref.7 D.L. Olson, “Prediction of Austenitic Weld Metal Microstructures and Properties”,
50 Welding Research Supplement 281-s, October 1985
51 Ref.8 G.F. Torkhov et al, “Nitrogen Behaviour in Liquid Iron-Chromium Alloys”,
52 Automatical Welding (in Russian), 10:16-20, 1971
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Ref.9 M. Sherif et al, SKF, US 2018073113A1, "Case-Hardenable Stainless Steel Alloy"

Ref.10 J-B. Coudert et al, "Assessment of Advanced Aerospace Bearing Steel RCF Performances Using a Discriminating Multicontact Test", Bearing Steel Technologies: 11th Volume, Progress in Steel Technologies and Bearing Steel Quality

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Phase diagram for P675

148x119mm (96 x 96 DPI)

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Phase diagram for alloy B with niobium micro-alloying

148x120mm (150 x 150 DPI)

delta-ferrite in alloy A

914x685mm (72 x 72 DPI)

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Image analysis in ImageJ
100x75mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Hardness profiles for the experimental alloys

127x76mm (150 x 150 DPI)

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Surface microstructure of alloy G

952x635mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Rod-like carbides in alloy B

952x635mm (72 x 72 DPI)

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Cobalt content and surface hardness

127x76mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Residual stress profiles for alloy D and alloy G

127x76mm (150 x 150 DPI)

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Schneider diagram [Ref.7]

199x119mm (120 x 120 DPI)

Correlation between nickel content and delta-ferrite content

127x76mm (150 x 150 DPI)

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Second phase in alloy H

203x144mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Hardness profiles of alloy J and P675 (LTT)

127x76mm (150 x 150 DPI)

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Hardness profiles of alloy J and P675 treated at 496 deg.C
128x76mm (150 x 150 DPI)